

POLICY CONFERENCE

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND
MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE
25 MARCH 2026, BRUSSELS

STRATEGIC ROADMAP

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Strategic Roadmap

**UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY
AND MARKET POTENTIAL
FROM WOOD WASTE**

STRATEGIC ROADMAP

- **EU's wood waste & fibreboard recycling context**
- **Key drivers & barriers**
- **Policy recommendations & research priorities**

Download: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17473127>

Policy Recommendations

Two groups of policy recommendations:

1. Maximising wood waste collection

2. Upgrading the quality of collected streams

Policy Recommendations

1. Maximising wood waste collection

Mobilise wood waste collection and recycling

Prioritise material use of wood over burning

Optimise storage for consistent wood waste supply

Policy Recommendations

1. Maximising wood waste collection

Mobilise wood waste collection and recycling

Prioritise material use of wood over burning

Optimise storage for consistent wood waste supply

Mobilise wood waste collection and recycling

1. Increase **collection volumes** as top priority

2. Encourage **take-back schemes** and reverse logistic

3. Provide **incentives for infrastructure** and logistics

Policy Recommendations

1. Maximising wood waste collection

Mobilise wood waste collection and recycling

Prioritise material use of wood over burning

Optimise storage for consistent wood waste supply

Prioritise material use of wood over bioenergy

1. **Recalibrate public support**

2. **Cascading as a binding operational principle**

3. **Encourage non-woody renewable energy**

Policy Recommendations

1. Maximising wood waste collection

Mobilise wood waste collection and recycling

Prioritise material use of wood over burning

Optimise storage for consistent wood waste supply

Optimise storage for consistent wood waste supply

1. Increase allowable storage limits :

- Adequate & flexible storage capacity
- Buffer seasonal peaks in supply and demand

Policy Recommendations

2. Upgrading the quality of collected streams

Modernise collection and sorting technologies

Efficient delivery of recyclable wood to material re-users

Policy Recommendations

2. Upgrading the quality of collected streams

Modernise collection and sorting technologies

Efficient delivery of recyclable wood to material re-users

Modernise collection and sorting technologies

1. Incentivised **separate collection (pre-processing, selective demolition)**

2. **Continuous improvement** of collection systems through EPR funds

3. **Targeted funding** for smart sorting & recycling technologies

Policy Recommendations

2. Upgrading the quality of collected streams

Modernise collection and sorting technologies

Efficient delivery of recyclable wood to material re-users

Efficient delivery of recyclable wood to material re-users

- 1. Set material re-users as the preferred destination of recyclable wood waste**

Key takeaways

1.

Make cascading a binding operational principle

2.

Maximise & improve wood waste collection systems

3.

Strengthen EU enabling conditions for circularity

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE

AT THE END THERE IS A SIMPLE PROMISE:

IF WE DON'T GIVE AWAY WOOD AND FIBREBOARD WASTE,

WE CAN USE IT AND ADD VALUE AGAIN.

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WHERE ARE WE NOW?

Drivers

- Industry's need to secure raw material supply
- Technical progress in sorting and defibration
- Growing market pull
- Policy momentum for the circular transition
- Climate and jobs benefits.

Barriers

- Regulatory disparities
- Fragmented and inconsistent collection systems
- Competition with energy recovery
- Logistical constraints, economic viability

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE

ECOReFIBRE 3+1 SOLUTION COMPONENTS

1

Design for circularity of products and processes

2

Efficient secondary materials markets

3

Secure high-quality supply at volume

4

Sustained multi-stakeholder dialogue
to foster the transition from linear value chains to circular value networks

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE

SUSTAINED MULTI-STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE
FOSTERING CIRCULAR VALUE NETWORKS

talk listen think

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Thank you!

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